

Metrological traceability for improved comparability of nucleic acid-based point-of-care testing for methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* diagnostics - A guidance document

Abstract

Due to the major public health concern, accelerated diagnostics of methicillin-resistance *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is crucial. Especially, the implementation of molecular nucleic acid-based point-of-care (POC) testing has already become widely established. However, currently available POC tests mostly based on quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) face methodological drawbacks. Here, we address manufacturers in particular identifying the obstacles to be overcome in developing tests with ever-shorter turnaround times (TAT) while ensuring test comparability between different instrument manufacturers, laboratories, or clinics. We present accessible standards of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) to establish metrological traceability, which is crucial for test reliability. Furthermore, we showcase how the implementation of the digital polymerase chain reaction (dPCR) method is revolutionizing conventional qPCR-based POC testings, making MRSA diagnostics more traceable, comparable, and thus reliable.

1. Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) indicates that methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) infections continue to be a major public health concern. MRSA is accounting for a significant number of healthcare-associated infections and an increasing incidence of community-acquired infections (Li et al., 2021). Furthermore, MRSA causes a wide range of serious infections in both high-risk and healthy patients (Coppens et al., 2019; A. S. Lee et al., 2018) including skin and soft tissue infections (Sanchini, 2022), pneumonia, osteoarticular infections, toxic shock syndrome, or bacteremia, which may be complicated by endocarditis or severe sepsis (Coppens et al., 2019). Specifically, *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) causes 70 - 80% of all wound infections, 50 - 60% of all osteomyelitis, 15-40% of all vascular prosthesis infections, up to 30% of all sepsis cases and 10% of all pneumonia cases

(Suerbaum et al., 2012). *S. aureus* bacteremia (SAB) is one of the most serious situations in *S. aureus* infections (Li et al., 2021; McNicholas et al., 2014). Therefore, test times must be as short as possible to allow targeted antibiotic intervention to prevent the spread of infection and organ failure.

The currently accepted gold standard for the detection of bacteria or fungi in blood, body fluids, or tissues, is still culture-based (Cohen et al., 2015; Liesenfeld et al., 2014; Mancini et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2022). In particular, the clinical diagnosis of bloodstream infections and bacterial identification depends on the results of conventional blood cultures, although these conventional methods are time-consuming and may require several days to generate a definitive result. However, the major drawback of conventional detection methods is the long time required to obtain a test result (Buonomini et al., 2020). In contrast to those conventional culture procedures, nucleic acid-based POC tests rapidly provide health professionals with actionable information concerning exactly the time and place of evaluation and treatment. Thus, the requirement for achieving a short TAT in diagnostic tests has driven the demand for POC testing (Wood, 2004). In MRSA diagnostics, molecular POC testing based on qPCR has become widely established, since they dramatically reduce the TAT (Li et al., 2021).

For common use in hospitals, POC testing requires high diagnostic accuracy to compete with general laboratory tests, whereas, low-resource settings, low-cost manufacture, long-term low-cost storage, and ease of use are dominant (Oeschger et al., 2019). Currently established molecular tests are rarely directly comparable with the observed cycle threshold numbers. The frequent contamination with other methicillin-resistant coagulase-negative *staphylococci* (MRCoNS) in clinical samples remains a major challenge in molecular POC testing. For example, the methicillin/ oxacillin resistance (*e.g.*, *mecA*) gene is also present in MRCoNS *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (*oxa^R*) (Mcdonald et al., 1995). Consequently, discrimination between MRSA and MRCoNS cannot be made in mixed cultures (van Belkum & Rochas, 2018). Thus, a comparative and confirmatory test based on conventional culture (*i.e.*, the gold standard) is essential (Ayebare et al., 2019; Sanchini, 2022)

As a national metrology institution (NMI), our mission is to increase awareness of the added value of metrological traceability in POC test manufacturing. Metrological

traceability is a key element to enhance comparability in nucleic acid-based POC tests. We highlight the priority of compliance with appropriate ISO standards. The implementation and use of certified reference material enhance the comparability of POC tests. In this way, test results obtained from various POC test providers and in different laboratories, are comparable. In this way, reliability, trust, and patient safety is being ensured in MRSA diagnostics.

2. State of the art in MRSA rapid diagnostics based on molecular nucleic acid assays

Over the last decade, microbial diagnosis of pathogens has substantially changed. In particular, molecular testing methods for the specific detection of nucleic acid sequences support clinical laboratory diagnostics (WHO, 2019). The WHO categorized molecular testing into sequencing, amplification, or hybridization methods. Sequencing methods are primarily used for the identification of organisms that are not cultivable or difficult to identify via conventional methods (Weile & Knabbe, 2009; WHO, 2019). Quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) based POC testing has become established in MRSA diagnostics. Those POC tests can be applied directly to blood samples (Cohen et al., 2015). In this way, the critical time to initiate prevention and treatment strategies is highly reduced. This includes the initiation point of adequate antibacterial treatments (Li et al., 2021). Time savings of up to 12-48 hours are possible in contrast to conventional cultivation-based methods (Buonomini et al., 2020). Especially, in rapid differentiation between MSSA and MRSA, nucleic acid amplification techniques are advantageous (van Belkum & Rochas, 2018). Recently, various molecular panels based on specific gene amplification have been developed for the rapid diagnosis of infectious syndromes. In hybridization assays, fluorescence-labeled oligonucleotide probes are used for species identification. In particular, hybridization assays are used favorably for the identification of slow-growing bacteria after isolation (WHO, 2019). In MRSA diagnostic, molecular techniques include but are not limited to qPCR, loop-mediated amplification (LAMP), PCR amplification combined with Invader[®] chemistry, or digital droplet recombinase polymerase amplification (ddRPA). A brief overview of available nucleic acid-based assays for rapid MRSA detection is given in table 1.

Table 1 Overview of molecular nucleic acid-based assays for rapid MRSA diagnostics.

MRSA Assay	Test Platform (Manufacturer)	Molecular Method (Target gene)	Matrix Type	TAT [min]	References
Digital single-cell detection, bi-plex					
Recombinase polymerase amplification (ddRPA) assay*	(non-commercial)	ddRPA (<i>mecA</i> , <i>vicK</i>)	Nasal swabs	55	(Schulz et al., 2020)
Eazyplex® MRSA*	Genie II MK2 (AmplexDiagnostics GmbH, Gars, Germany)	LAMP (<i>S. aureus</i> specific gene, <i>S. epidermidis</i> specific gene, <i>mecA</i> , and <i>mecC</i>)	Blood culture	15 - 60	(AmplexDiagnostics, 2022; Buonomini et al., 2020; Sanchini, 2022)
GENECUBE®	(TOYOBO Co., Ltd., Osaka, Japan)	Multiplex PCR (<i>nuc</i> , <i>mecA</i>)	Blood culture	52	(Hida et al., 2019)
GeneXpert® MRSA/SA SSTI *	GeneXpert® Dx System (Cepheid, Sunnyvale, USA)	Multiplex real-time PCR (<i>spa</i> , <i>mecA</i> , <i>SCCmec</i>)	Sputum and tissue samples	68-72	(Dubouix-Bourandy et al., 2011; Paonessa et al., 2019)
GeneXpert® NxG*	GeneXpert® Instrument Systems (Cepheid, Sunnyvale, USA)	Multiplex qPCR (<i>mecA</i> , <i>mecC</i> , <i>SCCmec</i>)	Nasal swabs	47 - 70	(Cepheid, 2019a)
GeneXpert® SA Nasal Complete*	GeneXpert® Dx System (Cepheid, Sunnyvale, USA)	Multiplex qPCR (<i>mecA</i> , <i>mecC</i> , <i>SCCmec</i>)	Nasal swabs	60-75	(Ayebare et al., 2019; Cepheid, 2019d)
GeneXpert® MRSA/SA BC*	GeneXpert® Instrument Systems (Cepheid, Sunnyvale, USA)	Multiplex qPCR (<i>mecA</i> , <i>mecC</i> , <i>SCCmec</i>)	Blood culture	60 - 102	(Cepheid, 2019b; McHugh et al., 2020)
LAMP-microfluidic chip	Microfluidic chip (non-commercial)	LAMP (<i>femA</i> , <i>mecA</i>)	Blood, urine, Bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL), sputum, drainage fluid	15 - 60	(Zhang et al., 2022)
MRSA/SA ELITE® MGB,	ELITE InGenius®, (ELITech Group, Puteaux, France)	Triplex real-time PCR (<i>S. aureus</i> specific gene, <i>mecA</i> , <i>mecC</i>)	Nasal swabs, blood culture, BAL, and culture isolates	150 - 180	(Boattini et al., 2020; Sanchini, 2022)
Multiplex PCR-based DNA	Chromatography-printed array strips, C-PAS	Multiplex PCR (<i>nuc</i> , <i>mecA</i> , <i>vanA/B</i>)	Blood culture	120	(Kashef & Helmy, 2022)

MRSA Assay	Test Platform (Manufacturer)	Molecular Method (Target gene)	Matrix Type	TAT [min]	References
lateral flow assay (MBDLFA)*	(non-commercial)				
Panther Fusion®	(Hologic Inc., Marlborough, USA)	Invader® chemistry	Nasal swabs	Within 180	(Maurin et al., 2020)

*Designated POC system

POC tests should meet the ASSURED criteria defined by the WHO. This acronym stands for affordable, sensitive, specific, user-friendly, rapid and robust, equipment-free, and deliverable to the end-user (Mabey et al., 2004). All of the above-listed tests are indeed established rapid tests for MRSA diagnostics. However, not all of them meet the ASSURED criteria. For instance, only portable devices are suitable for use at or near the POC. When comparing assays, commonalities, and variances of the detection methods need to be considered more in detail. Various nucleic acid-based POC tests have the same target sequences in common, *e.g.*, *mecA/B*. In addition, similar sample matrices like nasal swabs or blood cultures are used in several tests. The comparability of the assays is significantly influenced by method variations, *e.g.*, in PCR techniques, sample handling, or the sample matrix. In particular, the type of sample or the PCR technique impacts the TAT. For instance, the LAMP-based Eazyplex® MRSA test allows very fast screening times within 15 to 20 minutes from blood cultures or directly from swabs (AmplexDiagnostics, 2022). When using blood culture as a sample, it is essential to take the cultivation time into account in addition to the test-specified TAT. In this case, the cultivation time extends the TAT by at least another 23 hours (Hida et al., 2019). The TAT is reduced remarkably when using nasal swabs or sputum and tissue samples. Here, the analysis occurs directly after the sample collection from the patient and the incubation time is redundant. LAMP is a promising technology regarding short TATs. Although a large number of amplicons can be generated in less than an hour, sensitivity and specificity are limited by LAMP (WHO, 2019).

Ensuring the comparability of POC tests is essential. In particular, medical professionals expect reliable and comparable test results, even if they have been measured with different methods or in different laboratories. However, this expectation cannot be generalized. The lack of comparability makes it difficult to compare results between health systems and different laboratories. This leads to negative

consequences for the patient's outcome (Armbruster, 2007; Hernandez et al., 2010). The use of metrologically traceable reference materials and procedures ensures the comparability of diverse analytical systems. Although the test results are metrologically traceable themselves, they are not always comparable. Comparability is lacking if the assays are traceable to different reference standards and non-commutable materials are used. Differences in the analytical specificity or an enormous measurement uncertainty in the traceability hierarchy further lead to poor comparability (Armbruster, 2007). If the reference material is not commutable, the results of routine methods cannot be legitimately compared with the assigned value. It is not possible to determine whether the observed deviations are artifacts due to inadequate material or true biases between the methods being analyzed. Non-commutability of reference material may be, *e.g.*, due to a change in the sample matrix. The sample matrix includes all components of a material system except the analyte itself. A matrix effect or matrix bias can occur when the sample matrix of the reference material and the clinical samples differ significantly (Miller et al., 2006)

In conclusion, rapid tests based on PCR techniques are successful in MRSA diagnostics. The different test methods cannot be generally compared with each other. The comparability of test results from different laboratories and healthcare systems is critical for the patient's outcome. Here, the use of metrologically traceable reference measurements and materials is demanding.

3. Guidelines for the implementation of metrological traceability in the manufacturing of POC testing

The metrological traceability of POC tests ensures comparability. Accordingly, the measurement results generated by various POC test providers or laboratories are comparable. Thus, for the implementation and realization of metrological traceability in the manufacturing process, we state the importance of the use of available ISO standards. Table 2 lists relevant ISO standards, used in this guidance document, addressing metrological traceability. In addition, we present relevant guidelines for a quality management system and the necessary regulations to meet legal requirements. We also discuss the importance of the extensive calibration hierarchy of calibrators. This ensures that calibrators supplied by manufacturers are traceable to reference

materials and measurements (RMM) of the highest metrological order. Furthermore, we explain the use of external and internal control materials for quality control and show examples of suitable DNA target sequences for MRSA diagnosis. Finally, we provide guidelines for ensuring traceability to conventional reference measurement methods and show the added value of using intrinsically metrologically traceable methods such as digital PCR.

Table 2: Applicable guidelines for implementing metrological traceability in the manufacturing process of POC testings.

ISO Standard	Title	Guidance on Metrological Traceability	References
13485:2016	Medical devices — Quality management systems — Requirements for regulatory purposes	Requirements for a quality management system and documentation procedures, regulatory requirements	(International Organization of Standardization, 2016)
15194:2009	<i>In vitro</i> diagnostic medical devices — Measurement of quantities in samples of biological origin — Requirements for certified reference materials and the content of supporting documentation	Benefits of using reference material (RM) and requirements for certified reference material (CRM) considered of higher metrological order	(International Organization of Standardization, 2009)
17511:2003	<i>In vitro</i> diagnostic medical devices — Measurement of quantities in biological samples — Metrological traceability of values assigned to calibrators and control materials	Definition of measurable quantity and internalization of the calibration hierarchy	(International Organization of Standardization, 2003)
20395:2019	Biotechnology — Requirements for evaluating the performance of quantification methods for nucleic acid target sequences — qPCR and dPCR	Evaluation of the performance and quality assurance of nucleic acid-based quantification methods	(International Organization of Standardization, 2019)

3.1. Quality Management System in POCT manufacturing

To ensure general traceability, procedures must be documented within the quality management (QM) system of an organization involved in one or more stages of the life cycle of a medical device: in design and manufacture, storage and distribution, installation, maintenance, and final decommissioning or disposal of medical devices

and the provision of related activities such as technical support and/or post-market surveillance. The requirements and procedures for a complete quality management system are specified in ISO 13485:2016. These procedures define the scope of general traceability according to applicable regulatory requirements and the records to be maintained. The transparency of documentation procedures enables the traceability of the individual steps in the POC testing manufacturing process, leading to a safe product. Documentation procedures according to QM requirements ensure the metrological traceability chain. Traceability requires reference measurement systems and the use of reference standards. Therefore, organizations need to document procedures that define the scope of traceability in terms of applicable regulatory requirements and the records to be controlled. Record control includes the documentation of procedures that define the necessary controls (for identification, storage, security, integrity, retrieval, retention period, or disposal of records). It also includes documentation of procedures to maintain device compliance with regulatory requirements. This refers to the records relating to processing, storing, handling, and distributing the constituent parts of a medical device. Those records must remain legible, readily identifiable, and retrievable. Whenever changes are made, records must remain identifiable and should be retained for at least the lifetime of the medical device, nevertheless for at least two years after the release of the medical device. The lifetime is either determined by the organization or by regulatory requirements (International Organization of Standardization, 2016)

3.2 Extensive calibration hierarchy: linking reference material and measurements of the highest metrological order to calibrators

According to ISO 15194:2009, RM is used for the calibration of quantity values, validation or control of the trueness of measured values, and the evaluation of the performance of a new measurement procedure. In this way, the measurement results and the performance verification of the nucleic acid measurement process are analytically traceable (International Organization of Standardization, 2009). ISO 17511:2003 specifies further how to ensure the metrological traceability of the values assigned to calibrators and control materials. on which the accuracy of a measurement and its verification is based. Calibrators and control materials are supplied by

manufacturers as part of, or for common use with, an *in vitro* diagnostic (IVD) medical device (International Organization of Standardization, 2003)

By definition, metrological traceability is a property of a measurement result (Armbruster, 2007), which can be related to the International System of Units (*Système international d'unités*, SI) or other agreed standards or references (International Organization of Standardization, 2019). This relationship, which contributes to the uncertainty of measurement, is ensured by a documented, and unbroken calibration chain. A metrological traceability chain is therefore used to establish the metrological traceability of a measurement result (Armbruster, 2007). The use of traceable calibrators or RM promotes the comparability of systems from different manufacturers. This allows comparability of measurements even between different laboratories or clinics (Kristensen, 2001). The ideal starting point of a metrological traceability chain is the definition of the appropriate unit according to SI (International Organization of Standardization, 2003). Ideally, the RMM is available and traceable to SI (Armbruster, 2007). However, the available measurement methods and higher-order calibrators will determine the choice of steps and level at which metrological traceability for a given value ends (International Organization of Standardization, 2003). For example, if the RMM is both available but not traceable to SI, or only the RM or the measurement procedure, or neither is available (Armbruster, 2007). In such cases, trueness is referred to the calibration hierarchy level until an internationally agreed RMM is available (International Organization of Standardization, 2003). Manufacturers should adhere to the extensive calibration hierarchy model by ISO 17511:2003. Thus, the provided calibrators are linked to the RMM of the highest metrological order. Accordingly, RMs of higher metrological order are categorized as measurement standards by their positions in the reference measurement system for a given quantity (primary, secondary, and international conventional calibrator). Primary calibrators and reference procedures, provided by the International Bureau of Weights and Measures (*Bureau International des Poids et Mesures*, BIPM), national metrology institutes (NMIs), or accredited reference measurement laboratories (NRLs), show high metrological traceability to SI and the lowest combined standard uncertainty (u_c) in the calibration chain. Further down the calibration hierarchy, u_c is increasing. Secondary reference measurements and calibrators are defined by NMIs and NRLs as well. Following the secondary calibrators, working calibrators and product calibrators are

positioned. Both the working and product calibrators and measurement procedures are provided by the manufacturer. Hence, the manufacturer's responsibility for metrological traceability begins with the assigned value for a product calibrator and ends with the secondary calibrator or secondary reference measurement procedure. Following the product calibrators, routine measurements of clinical/patient samples are provided by the end user. At the end of the calibration chain, the patient results are located with the highest u_c . This demonstrates that traceability hierarchy and measurement uncertainty define the metrological traceability of a measurement result. Furthermore, an unbroken calibration chain is crucial to obtain patient results with a defined uncertainty traceable to SI. In this way, it is possible to compare patient results with those of other manufacturers and between different laboratories. In general, RM should be characterized concerning (international) recognition, issuing authority (*i.e.*, WHO), certified/not-certified, origin, production (*e.g.*, synthetic), molecular forms, matrix, state of aggregation, phase, and the intended use (International Organization of Standardization, 2003). In particular, CRM provides trustworthy reference values. A CRM contains one or more property values certified by a technically valid process. Furthermore, CRMs have commutable properties, thus, a similar matrix to that of the test sample and a copy number concentration of the target DNA within the same range as the routine samples (International Organization of Standardization, 2019) In addition, CRM is accompanied or traceable by a certificate or other document issued by a certification authority. Since CRMs are well characterized with known content and a defined uncertainty, their use provides reliable and comparable results (Quevauviller & Drève de Nivelles, 2019).

3.3. Quality controls for PCR performance validation

By providing internal quality controls, the manufacturer provides control of the whole analysis process including the sample processing, the appropriate amplification reactions, and the function of the reaction reagents. In this way, the analytical traceability of the PCR measurement results and the performance verification of the nucleic acid measurement process is ensured. To identify bias in pre-analytical steps, external calibration may be required. If calibrators are used, the performance of the calibrators should be similar to that of the samples of interest. Sample preparation is

crucial concerning the quality of PCR experiments and the source for substantial experimental variations. Therefore, detailed documentation of sample processing and extraction steps is essential. Depending on the sample material, certain sample collection and handling methods have major effects on PCR results (Whale et al., 2020). Sample process controls (SPC) may be necessary to reveal systematic errors related to pre-analytical steps (e.g., DNA extraction). For example, the amount of available nucleic acid concentration varies depending on the DNA extraction (Whale et al., 2020). Furthermore, SPCs confirm correct reagent rehydration, PCR tube filling in the system, probe integrity, as well dye stability. Inaccuracies in specimen processing or the presence of PCR inhibitors in swab specimens, including mucin, blood, dust, or air bubbles, could result in inhibitory effects and therefore invalid PCR results (Ayebare et al., 2019). These inhibitors such as sample preparation reagents or excessive protein can cause partial or complete inhibition of downstream PCR (International Organization of Standardization, 2019) and consequently to false results depending on the type of inhibitor, the number of amplicons, or the sample type (Huggett et al., 2008; Suslov & Steindler, 2005). An SPC might include dried bacteria spores derived from *Bacillus globii* (Cepheid, 2019d, 2019b, 2019c), demonstrating that lysis of *S. aureus*, if present, has occurred and verifying appropriate sample processing. However, occasionally manufacturers do not share any further information on the content of the SPC which makes the comparison between different systems difficult.

ISO 20395:2019 describes the requirements to measure the impact of the sample matrix on assay performance and measure specific PCR inhibition. The presence and extent of inhibition may be determined by preparing control reactions containing: the internal PCR control spiked into extracted sample matrix, the internal PCR control only in absence of extracted sample matrix, and the extracted sample matrix only to determine the background concentration of the nucleic acid target. Furthermore, inhibitor concentration is reduced via sample dilution. In addition, the analysis of individual reaction kinetics or the amplification efficiency is necessary to measure the impact of the sample matrix on assay performance (International Organization of Standardization, 2019). Since matrix effects could interfere with the PCR results, the used RM should be spiked in the same or similar matrices as those used in routine patient samples (Vesper et al., 2007). Therefore, the manufacturer could specify

simulated matrices used for analytical performance studies to evaluate the LOD and bacterial or chemical interference. For example, the manufacturer states the content of simulated matrices used for the performance evaluation of the GeneXpert®MRSA POC test. For instance, simulated nasal matrixes consisting of mucin and blood, simulated negative blood culture, or surrogate wound matrices contain white blood cell concentrate, red blood cells, plasma, and anticoagulants, as stated by the manufacturer (Cepheid, 2019a, 2019c, 2019d, 2019b).

3.4 Suitable target sequences for MRSA point-of-care diagnostics

Commonly available duplex assays are based on the detection of methicillin /oxacillin resistance genes, and specific genes for *S. aureus* simultaneously. For example, the methicillin /oxacillin resistance gene *mecA* encodes for the protein binding protein 2a (PBP2a), a peptidoglycan transpeptidase that has become an established method for molecular MRSA identification (Katayama et al., 2000). MRSA strains carry an altered PBP2a with reduced binding affinity for penicillin. The *mecA* gene is located on the staphylococcal cassette chromosome *mec* (SCCmec), which is a mobile genetic element and is located in the *orfX* locus of the *S. aureus* genome (Buonomini et al., 2020; Katayama et al., 2000; Sanchini, 2022). At present, 14 SCCmec types have been identified (Sanchini, 2022). The *mecC* gene, a *mecA* homologous determinant, has been identified for MRSA (J. H. Lee et al., 2004; Sanchini, 2022). However, the detection of the *mecA* gene will not detect resistance mechanisms such as *mecC* (J. H. Lee et al., 2004; Madhavan et al., 2021). The majority of commercially available tests share a high risk of false-positive results based on single or double locus detection. Singleplex assays target the 3'-end of the SCCmec element, the *orfX*-SCCmec junction, overlooking that in some strains the *mecA* gene can be partially deleted or lost. These include variations in SCCmec sequences and also variations in chromosomal loci that identify organisms as *S. aureus*, such as *spa* and *nuc* (Tenover & Tickler, 2022). Since new SCCmec variants emerge, primers need to be redesigned and the assay needs to be revalidated regularly (Schulz et al., 2020).

However, a major drawback of these detection methods is that they cannot distinguish MRSA from a mixture of MSSA and methicillin-resistant coagulase-negative staphylococci (MRCoNS) if both are present in clinical samples. This results in low

specificity (<62%) and low positive predictive values (<85%). As a solution, the approach of combining single-cell analysis and duplex PCR detection could provide a solution to this issue. To distinguish MRSA from MRCoNS, it is essential to have the genetic information of only one species. Here, via the microfluidic system, the distribution of the bacteria relies on the singularization of particles into single droplets following the Poisson statistics. In this way, the different bacterial species can be separated during the emulsification process (Ferreira et al., 2018; Li et al., 2021; Schulz et al., 2020; Weile & Knabbe, 2009).

3.5 Traceability to the reference gold standard

The current gold standard for the detection of MRSA is the conventionally culture-based approach where broth enrichment culture is combined with plate culture and the identification of methicillin/oxacillin resistance by various techniques *e.g.*, antibiotic susceptibility screening tests on oxacillin-selective agar (Schulz et al., 2020; Tenover & Tickler, 2022). For ensuring the comparability, and thus traceability, of molecular POC test results, they still rely on those of the gold standard reference method. For example, to evaluate whether any isolate is false positive or define a sample as positive by the reference standard if it tested positive (Ayebare et al., 2019). For traceability reasons, manufacturers should share information on comparative reference procedures for investigating the performance characteristics of the POC tests. For example, certain manufacturers already indicate that a comparative reference method could consist of both a direct culture on MRSA selective chromogenic agar and enriched culture (Cepheid, 2019a). This information makes it possible to trace the specific test performance back to a particular reference method. In this way, test results are metrologically traceable. In this context, we recommend the use of accredited reference material to ISO 17034, *e.g.*, such strains derived from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC®). Especially for the discrimination between MRSA, MSSA, or MRCoNS, *S. aureus* subsp. *aureus* Rosenbach (American Type Culture Collection (ATCC®), 2023b; American Type Culture Collection (ATCC®), 2023c) could serve as an external positive control strain, and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (*S. epidermidis*) (American Type Culture Collection (ATCC®), 2023a).

3.6. Digital PCR for metrologically traceable results

Digital PCR (dPCR) have an added value regarding metrological traceability. The dPCR technique has the potential to provide traceability to SI due to the capability of counting all amplifiable DNA molecules containing a specific target sequence. Quantities like copies of a particular nucleic acid sequence have the unit one, which is by nature an element of any system of units and thus, is traceable to SI (International Organization of Standardization, 2019). It is a promising technique to perform metrologically traceable measurements and quantification of the RM. Thus, different laboratories can achieve comparable results (International Organization of Standardization, 2003).

ISO standard 20395:2019. addresses measurement traceability and comparability for PCR-based nucleic acid quantification and offers best practices to maximize the potential impact of the capacity of traceable DNA quantification. It provides general requirements for the performance evaluation and quality assurance for the quantification of nucleic acid sequences. Furthermore, this ISO standard outlines that dPCR, as an enumeration-based measurement procedure, provides the basis for a primary reference measurement method for nucleic acid copy number quantification. Appropriate, validated measurement procedures result in formal traceability to SI (International Organization of Standardization, 2019).

The technological potential of dPCR is further presented in *The Digital MIQE Guidelines* (dMIQE) Update. These guidelines stipulate minimum reporting requirements for standardization, and thus, successful replication of dPCR experiments. Accordingly, detailed information about specimens, nucleic acid extraction, -assessment and storage, reverse transcription, oligonucleotide and target design, dPCR protocol, assay validation, and data analysis are essential. Moreover, dMIQE presents how to, maximize the efficient utilization of resources, and further enhance the impact of the dPCR technology. In addition, dMIQE advises ensuring scientific integrity and a facilitated replication of experiments and provides critical information allowing measuring the technical quality of submitted manuscripts against an established standard. Only compliance with these guidelines ensures metrological traceability regarding the definition and characterization of RMM based on dPCR (Whale et al., 2020)

4. Conclusion

In this guidance document, the need for comparable POC testing in nucleic acid-based MRSA diagnostics is highlighted. Here, we demonstrate the added value of metrological traceability for enhanced comparability of POC tests. Furthermore, we provide metrological guidance in compliance with ISO guidelines. Only metrologically traceable POC testing, independently from testing site and method, leads to comparable test results between different health care systems and laboratories. In particular, during the manufacturing process, POC test providers must implement metrological traceability via 1) ensuring the general traceability chain of procedures; 2) linking RMM of the highest metrological order to calibrators and target DNA sequences; 3) applying detection methods that are metrologically traceable to the reference gold standard (*i.e.*, culture-based methods). Here, we recommend the use of accredited reference material to ISO 17034, *e.g.*, strains derived from ATCC®. Furthermore, certified RMMs, provided by the issuing authorities (*i.e.*, WHO, NMIs, or NRLs) ensure traceability to SI. As a further step to be followed, manufacturers must evaluate the benefit of dPCR technology concerning MRSA POC test development, since this technology offers traceable DNA quantification to SI. In this way, the reliability and comparability of MRSA testing will be enhanced ensuring reliability, trust, and patient safety in MRSA diagnostics.

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